

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Knowledge, Attitude and Perception of Fisherfolks on Anthropogenic activities in Capiz

OPEN ACCESS

Received: 17-10-2024

Accepted: 20-11-2024

Published: 08-01-2025

Citation: Pimentel SS, Linan EL, Florentino JS, Bardinas FGV, Berondo RG, Legaspi JS, Bicular LAB (2025) Knowledge, Attitude and Perception of Fisherfolks on Anthropogenic activities in Capiz. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 18(1): 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v18i1.3425>

* **Corresponding author.**sspimentel@capsu.edu.ph**Funding:** CAPSU RDE**Competing Interests:** None

Copyright: © 2025 Pimentel et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.isee.org))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Stephanie S Pimentel^{1*}, Efren L Linan², Joemel S Florentino³,
Favie Gelyn V Bardinas³, Ronilo G Berondo⁴, Jocelyn S Legaspi⁵,
Leo Andrew B Bicular⁶

¹ Research Director, Capiz State University, Roxas City, Capiz, Philippines

² University President, Capiz State University, Roxas City, Capiz, Philippines

³ Fisheries and Food Research Development Center, Philippines

⁴ Capiz State University, Roxas City, Capiz, Philippines

⁵ Extension Director, Capiz State University, Roxas City, Capiz, Philippines

⁶ VP RDE, Capiz State University, Roxas City, Capiz, Philippines

Abstract

Objectives: This study aims to assess the anthropogenic activities of fisherfolks in Capiz as well as their impacts on coastal areas, issues they face, and their knowledge and attitudes towards environmental preservation. **Methods:** This study utilized a mixed-method approach that combines qualitative and quantitative approaches. Recorded interviews were utilized to collect qualitative data in the form of one on one interviews and focus group discussions. A five-point scale questionnaire was used to measure the level of knowledge of the respondents towards the importance of coastal areas and their attitudes toward their preservation, maintenance, protection, and rehabilitation. **Findings:** Multiple anthropogenic activities were evaluated in the coastal municipalities of Capiz, which have both positive and negative impacts on the environment. On the positive side, they participate in coastal clean-up drives, mangrove planting, recycling and waste segregation, proper waste disposal, implementing closed seasons for fishing, the Basura Baylo Bugas program (a waste-for-rice exchange initiative), and sustainable shellfish collection. These activities contribute to environmental conservation and sustainable resource management. However, there are also harmful practices such as illegal fishing, mangrove cutting, over-collection or irresponsible shellfish collection, setting up multiple fishing gears, improper waste disposal, and irresponsible local tourism. Moreover, the fisherfolks within these coastal municipalities demonstrated a high level of knowledge regarding the importance of coastal areas. More than half of respondents, or 68.11 percent have a highly favorable attitude towards coastal conservation. **Novelty:** This study reveals the multiple anthropogenic activities in the coastal municipalities of Capiz. It uncovers the current status of the coastal communities in relation to the conservation of coastal areas.

Keywords: Sustainability; Biodiversity; Livelihood; Ecosystem; Management

1 Introduction

Anthropogenic activities are human activities that negatively impact aquatic ecosystems which could be in the form of sewage, nutrients, crude oil, heavy metals, and plastics⁽¹⁾. This activity changes the equilibrium between the elements of coastal and aquatic environments where these changes cause stress physiology and behavior within and among organisms, affecting ecological relationships and cascading effects across interaction networks⁽²⁾. Additionally, anthropogenic activities in coastal marine ecosystems enhance the population of potentially hazardous microbes, resulting in different microbial communities that have negative consequences for marine macrobiota⁽³⁾. Coastal eutrophication is caused by anthropogenic nutrient inputs, which result in "dead zones," habitat loss, and toxic phytoplankton blooms⁽⁴⁾. Generally, anthropogenic activities destroy habitats, hasten biodiversity loss, and increase exposure to chemical contaminants, all of which have impacts on ocean health⁽⁵⁾.

From the above literature, it generalizes that the threat to coastal ecosystems has raised major concerns from anthropogenic activities. However, while anthropogenic activities have contributed to numerous environmental challenges, it also drove advancements in human society⁽⁶⁾. Previous literature focuses on the analyses of the results of activities such as pollution and chemical imbalance and the general concepts of anthropogenic activities that impact the coastal and marine environments. This method is more on the reactive side since knowing the effect is after the fact that the anthropogenic activities were carried out. The present study focuses on the activities and first-hand experiences of the fisherfolks which impacts both negatively and positively towards the coastal areas. It also investigates the extent of knowledge of these communities and their conservation attitudes. By providing new data on the activities and experiences of the fisherfolks in the coastal region, more accurate interventions can be formulated that directly target harmful activities and promote beneficial practices toward the coastal ecosystem. Humans are the primary driver of anthropogenic change derived from their anthropogenic activities⁽⁷⁾, so it is reasonable to focus on the fisherfolks as they are closely entwined with the coastal ecosystems.

Fisherfolks of coastal municipalities in the Province of Capiz are those that are located along the coastal areas and often rely on these waters as a source of their livelihoods and way of life. Their knowledge of coastal environments and their attitudes towards coastal conservation could have significant impacts on the challenges and opportunities that they face, and looking into these factors can inform efforts to support and improve the quality of life for these communities. This research study focuses on the fisherfolk communities of coastal municipalities in the Province of Capiz, who rely on the coastal areas for their livelihoods. Capiz's coastal areas are vulnerable to different natural disasters and are the first to be hit by storm surges and rising sea levels. Fisherfolks should be given attention as seafood catch diversity in the area is in decline⁽⁸⁾. Upland problems such as chemical pollution end up in the coastal regions, making them much more vulnerable to different problems. The study is driven by the understanding that the cultural practices of these communities significantly impact the challenges and opportunities that they face. Highlighting the unfavorable effects of human activities on ecosystems⁽⁹⁾, this study underscores the urgent need to address these impacts, most especially in light of the high poverty incidence among fisherfolk identified by the Philippine Statistics Authority in 2020. In 2021, the number of registered municipal fisherfolk was 2,190,438 who were engaged in capture fishing (50.03%), gleaning (11.59%), and aquaculture (11.28%). The rest were involved either

in fish vending, fish processing, and other fishery-related activities⁽¹⁰⁾.

Based on previous findings that emphasize the degrading state of the environment, this study aims to assess the anthropogenic activities of fisherfolks in Capiz as well as their impacts on coastal areas, issues they face, and their knowledge and attitudes towards environmental preservation.

2 Methodology

2.1 Research Design

This study utilized a mixed method approach that combines qualitative and quantitative approaches. The purposive sampling method was employed in the identification of the study’s respondents to ensure alignment of the study’s objectives and the attributes of the representative sample. The quantitative approach in this study was used to determine the level of knowledge of the coastal community towards social, economic, cultural and ecological importance of coastal areas as well as to global warming and climate change and their attitudes towards its preservation, maintenance, protection, and rehabilitation. The qualitative approach in this research study was conducted to know the respondent’s anthropogenic activities that affect coastal areas. The study was carried out between September 2023 and May 2024.

2.2 Research Gap

This study aims to bring to light the multiple activities of fisherfolks in the coastal municipalities of Capiz. By uncovering different beneficial and harmful activities, more effective intervention and rehabilitation programs can be initiated not only for the identified coastal areas but also for the fisherfolks in the coastal communities. Their knowledge and attitude towards coastal conservation were also assessed to determine whether further knowledge enhancement programs are necessary since it is established that knowledge and attitude contribute to their activities. In-person interviews and focus group discussions as the primary methods in this study ensure an accurate description of what is actually happening in the identified areas compared to projections and estimated data.

2.3 Methods of research

A mixed-method approach was employed in this study. A questionnaire was administered to a total of 392 respondents to assess their level of knowledge and attitude. An interview session then followed to collect qualitative data regarding their anthropogenic activities, perceptions, and problems or challenges. The interview questions were pre-tested and translated to the local dialect to facilitate understanding. Voice recordings of the interviews were transcribed. A quota of respondents was set to 14 individuals for every barangay/coastal community, and convenience sampling was employed to maximize the availability of the respondents. The respondents were limited to the fisherfolks of the identified coastal community.

To facilitate the consolidation of data and application of appropriate statistical tools, a five-point scale was utilized namely: “not aware”, “slightly aware”, “neutral”, “aware” and “fully aware” given a point of 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 respectively. On attitude, similar 5-point scoring is used. All data gathered were consolidated and generally expressed in descriptive measures such as frequencies, means, and percentages. Variables in the study were categorized as follows:

Table 1. Categorization of Variables

Level of Knowledge of the Respondents	
Scale	Verbal Interpretation
4.20- 5.0	Very High
3.40- 4.19	High
2.60-3.39	Average
1.80-2.59	Low
1.0- 1.79	Very Low
Level of Attitude of the Respondents	
Scale	Verbal Interpretation
4.20- 5.0	Very Favorable
3.40- 4.19	Favorable
2.60-3.39	Neutral
1.80-2.59	Unfavorable
1.0- 1.79	Very Unfavorable

2.4 Study site and respondents of the study

Seven (7) municipalities in the province which identified to have coastal communities were the study site as shown in Table 2 with the specific coastal barangays.

Table 2. Study site

MUNICIPALITY	BARANGAY	TOTAL RESPONDENTS
Sapian	Lonoy, Agtatacay, Agsilab	42
Ivisan	Balaring, Basiao, Cabugao, Agustin Navarra	56
Roxas City	Barra, Cogon, Culasi, Olotayan, Talon, Punta Cogon	84
Panay	Agojo, Bantigue, Bontod, Butacal, Jamul-awon, Lat-asan, Navitas	98
Pontevedra	Cabugao, Gabuc, San Pedro	42
President Roxas	Pinamihagan, Madulano	28
Pilar	Binaobawan, Guise Dulangan, Poblacion	42

Fig 1. Study site

The respondents are fisherfolks in these coastal municipalities wherein the majority primarily rely on fishing supplemented by various roles. The study categorized data based on occupational roles within the fishing industry, as all respondents are involved in this field. This includes primary fishing roles which are respondents who are fishers; supporting roles which include essential activities such as equipment maintenance, catch processing, logistics, and merchandizing tasks; and seasonal roles or part-time workers due to fluctuating demands and seasonal variations and alternative economic sources. Table 3 shows the distributions of the respondents from the three roles.

Table 3. Role distribution

ROLES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Primary Fishing	248	63.26
Supporting	62	15.82
Seasonal	82	20.92
TOTAL	392	100.00

The sample population primarily composed of adults, with the 35-49 years age group as the most prominent. Family size on the 392 respondents has a varied distribution across different categories: 9.18 percent of the group are small families (1-2 members), while a larger proportion, or 44.13 percent, falls within the medium-sized families (3-4 members). Also, 46.69 percent of the respondents were large families (5 members and above).

Education levels are mostly at the basic level, which may limit access to higher-paying jobs. While high homeownership can provide some stability, it does not ensure that there is financial security. Widespread dependence on government handouts and credit, with high finance stress, indicates much greater financial insecurity. Almost equal proportions of savers and non-savers suggest how financially insecure many household heads are.

3 Results and Discussion

The following is the assessment of the anthropogenic activities of fisherfolks in coastal municipalities in the Province of Capiz. Results and discussions were divided into these parts: Anthropogenic Activities; Level of Knowledge on Coastal Areas; Attitude Towards Coastal Area Preservation; Relationship between knowledge and conservation attitudes; and Problems and Issues.

3.1 Anthropogenic activities

The following are the anthropogenic activities conducted by fisherfolk within the coastal municipalities of Capiz.

Table 4. Anthropogenic activities

Beneficial Activities	Harmful Activities
1. Coastal Clean Up Drives	1. Illegal Fishing
2. Mangrove Planting	2. Mangrove Cutting
3. Recycling and Waste Segregation	3. Over collection/Irresponsible Shellfish Collection
4. Burying of Waste	4. Setting up multiple fishing gears
5. Implementing Close Season	5. Improper waste disposal
6. Basura Baylo Bugas Program (a waste-for-rice exchange initiative)	6. Irresponsible Local Tourism
7. Sustainable Shellfish Collection	

Coastal clean-up is a common practice in multiple coastal communities within Capiz, with frequencies ranging from weekly to monthly. These efforts are primarily organized by barangay officials, local government units (LGUs), and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) focused on coastal rehabilitation. Significant coastal clean-up activities have been reported in ten barangays, including Balarang, Poblacion Pilar, Navitas, Punta Cogan, Cabugao Pontevedra, Agustin Navarra, Butacal, Agsilab, and Culasi.

In Barangay Agustin Navarra, funds are allocated just for the purpose of mangrove planting, resulting in over 100 hectares of coastal land now covered with mature mangroves. In Agojo, many respondents suggested increasing mangrove planting activities, since they believe that organized efforts are more effective and have a more environmental impact. Mangrove planting is also widely practiced in Barangays of Binaobawan, Butacal, and Lonoy, while some barangays reported no mangrove planting activities due to unsuitable landscapes.

Recycling and waste segregation are also activities which are mentioned by the respondents. These are practiced in Basiao, Butacal, Lat-asan, and Cogan, where waste disposal is a challenge. Respondents reported recycling and reusing all materials that can be repurposed. Additionally, burying waste was reported, especially in barangays, such as Lat-asan, Jamul-awon, Cogan, and Olotayan, where waste collection is difficult.

In Poblacion Pilar, the Barangay Council has taken a proactive step in waste management by implementing the “Basura Baylo Bugas Program”. With this program, the residents receive a kilo of rice for every 2 kilos of recyclable plastics they bring, and so far it has proven to be a successful model for waste management. The program, recently launched, has effectively incentivized residents to collect multiple recyclable plastics, thereby reducing the amount of plastic waste that ends up in the sea. This incentive system for waste management has been proven effective, stating that the “concept of rewards motivates people to be conscious of ethical plastic usage and disposal⁽¹¹⁾. Thus, enabling municipalities to manage the disposed waste efficiently. The rewards could be customized based on the deployment scenario.”

Implementing various regulations, such as a close fishing season or the prohibition of catching certain species of fish affects the activities of fisherfolks. Respondents from Agustin Navarra and Navitas avowed that they restrict their catches due to the implementation of such regulations. In other data, a close season policy should be implemented along with other management strategies that will reduce fishing efforts even after the closure for it to have a significant impact⁽¹²⁾. In Guise, Dulangan, respondents practice sustainable shellfish collection by culturing the Asiatic Hard Clam (Kagaykay) to ensure both harvests and the preservation of the shellfish population.

On the other hand, anthropogenic activities that harm or destroy coastal areas were also noted. Illegal fishing was the most frequently mentioned activity, cited by respondents from Balarang, Bantigue, Butacal, Punta Cogan, Cabugao, Guise Dulangan,

Pinamihagan, Olotayan, and San Pedro in Pontevedra. Although illegal fishing is banned in all these areas, some activities persist based on respondents’ narratives. The illegal fishing techniques performed include trawl, birra-bira, balaybay, and fine-net fishing. Hudhud, mentioned as illegal by respondents from San Pedro, Pontevedra, is legal in other coastal communities. The continued illegal fishing activities pose a grave threat to the local marine ecosystem, leading to an imbalance in the fish population and imperiling the fishing industry. Illegal fishing activities also result in the decline in the quality of catches and depletion of the fish stocks, as well as the decline in the livelihood of fisherfolks⁽¹³⁾. Another illegal activity is the cutting down of mangroves. Respondents reported that illegal mangrove cutting occasionally occurs as people use the wood for firewood. It was noted that cutting small branches of mangrove trees is allowed only in certain areas to permit the passage of boats for transportation.

The irresponsible over-collection of shellfish is another destructive activity in the coastal areas of Capiz. Balaring, Basiao, and Lonoy respondents reported this activity in their areas. In Lonoy specifically, respondents narrated that people from other barangays or even municipalities collect shellfish from their shores, digging up to 2-3 sacks of shellfish every day. Moreover, in areas such as Agtatacay Sur and Pinamihagan, which is located within rivers approaching the sea, the setting up of multiple fishing gear in the river is a problem. The river becomes overcrowded and difficult to navigate.

Improper disposal of waste is an issue in all of the areas, involving problems such as waste collection and unmindful throwing of waste directly into the water. Despite this ongoing issue, respondents from every coastal community assessed that it is manageable with the intervention of barangay laws and ordinances. Respondents from Culasi reported a specific problem with local tourism, citing that visitors often leave their waste in the area. This can pose a problem since overnight tourist stays generate at least 22% more municipal solid waste, probably up to 55% more than local residents⁽¹⁴⁾.

3.1.1 Impact of anthropogenic activities to coastal community

Table 5. Impact of anthropogenic activities to coastal community

Anthropogenic activities	Occurrence in every municipalities	Impact on coastal community as perceived by the respondents
A. Coastal Clean Up Drives	Sapian, Ivisan, Roxas City, Panay	The respondents noted that this are the usual activity that they perform. According to them, this is an effective and fast way to clean their coastlines to reduce the dangers that contaminants could bring to their waters. Additionally, this activity increases the cooperation and collaboration initiatives of the fisherfolks.
B. Mangrove Planting	Sapian, Ivisan, Panay	“The more mangrove we have, the safer we are to strong winds and waves” is the prominent response when the respondents are asked of the impact of these activities to them. Also, they highlighted that mangroves are the breeding areas of different aquatic animals.
C. Recycling and Waste Segregation	Ivisan, Roxas City, Panay	It does not only beautify the coastal area but also prevents further problems from occurring.
D. Burying of Waste	Roxay City, Panay	In some areas where waste collection is impossible, this is the primary option that prevents the spread of the waste.
E. Implementing Close Season	Ivisan, Panay	Can disrupt the fishing activities abruptly but the fisherfolks are aware that this is also a way to preserve their resources as they need it for long-term livelihood.
F. “Basura Baylo Bugas Program”	Pilar	In addition to the minimized plastic waste that goes to the ocean this also helps the community alleviate food insecurity. This is a way to involve the community in conservation.
G. Sustainable Shellfish Collection	Roxas City, Pilar	Just like the Close seasons, shellfish collectors limit their shellfish collection as this gives time for the shells to grow. Respondents stressed that it would be difficult for them if all the shellfish were collected since there’s nothing left to spawn.
H. Illegal Fishing	Ivisan, Roxas City, Pontevedra, President Roxas, Pilar	Illegal fishing practices deplete fish stocks, disrupting marine ecosystems and threatening the livelihoods of law-abiding fisherfolk.
I. Mangrove Cutting	Ivisan, Panay, Pontevedra, Pilar	This destroys the natural habitat of marine organisms. Also, the efforts for mangrove planting activities become useless leading to unproductive cycle replanting.

Continued on next page

Table 5 continued

J. Over collection/Irresponsible Shellfish Collection	Sapian, Ivisan	When over-collected, species of certain shellfish could be depleted or completely lost in certain areas. This situation has already happened in some parts of the study site.
K. Setting up multiple fishing gears	Sapian, President Roxas	Stationary fishing gears constantly catch all marine organisms from the time they are set up, which results in a rapid decrease in their population. It also accelerates the rate of siltation that disturbs the natural flow of water.
L. Improper waste disposal	Sapian, Ivisan, Roxas City, Panay, Pontevedra, Resident Roxas, Pilar	Many wastes and garbage are being washed ashore. Respondents noticed that waste even from other communities is being washed into their areas which affects them negatively, pollutes their waters and destructs their resources.
M. Irresponsible Local Tourism	Roxas City	Many waste left in coastal areas that reduce its aesthetic and recreational value.

3.2 Level of Knowledge of Coastal Areas

This part discusses the respondents’ level of knowledge regarding the social, economic, cultural, and ecological importance of coastal areas and the relationship between conditions in Capiz and global warming or climate change.

As shown in Table 6, 48.98 percent of the respondents obtained a very high level of knowledge. Additionally, thirty-eight and one hundredth (38.01) percent of the total sample population had a high level of knowledge. The remaining respondents (13.01%) obtained an average level of knowledge. Overall, the data revealed that the respondents had a high level of knowledge regarding the social, economic, cultural, and ecological importance of coastal areas and the relationship between conditions in Capiz and global warming or climate change, as indicated by the mean of 4.14.

Almost half of the respondents (192 out of 392 individuals) obtained a “Very high” level of knowledge regarding the social, economic, cultural, and ecological importance of coastal areas and the relationship between conditions in Capiz and global warming or climate change. This indicates a strong awareness among fisherfolk in Capiz coastal communities regarding the extreme impact of coastal areas on their lives. This “very high” level of knowledge is crucial since resilience and community-based conservation can be improved by incorporating indigenous and local knowledge into coastal ecosystem management⁽¹⁵⁾. This highlights the importance of individuals having a high level of knowledge in managing coastal areas for rehabilitation and maintenance in their communities. Furthermore, even with low levels of education, coastal communities’ decisions to engage in conservation initiatives like mangrove rehabilitation are greatly influenced by their degree of knowledge⁽¹⁶⁾.

Table 6. Level of knowledge

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Very High	192	48.98
High	149	38.01
Average	51	13.01
TOTAL	392	100.00
Mean = 4.14 (High)		

3.3 Attitudes towards Conservation of Coastal areas

This part assesses the attitude of the respondents towards the preservation, maintenance, protection, and rehabilitation of coastal areas in Capiz. The respondents’ answers to the questionnaire were scored, and their level of attitude is described in terms of their favorability towards statements about the conservation of the coastal areas. According to the data in Table 7, 68.11 percent of the respondents had a highly favorable attitude toward the conservation of coastal areas. 30.10 percent of the total sample respondents expressed a favorable attitude, while a small percentage (1.79%) remained neutral. Overall, the data indicates that the respondents generally had a very favorable attitude towards the preservation, maintenance, protection, and rehabilitation of coastal areas in Capiz, with a mean score of 4.32.

A highly favorable attitude towards conservation strongly reflects the positive outlook of the respondents in regard to sustainable utilization of their natural resources. In support of this observation, a study on “The Role of Hope and Conservation Attitudes in Current Conservation Actions and Future Conservation Intentions,” found that positive attitude correlates with engagement in conservation actions⁽¹⁷⁾. A positive attitude toward conservation may depend on several factors, which include

the benefits respondents receive from conserved areas. This implies that the high dependence of respondents on coastal areas translates to a very important value attached to these regions, thus leading to a very favorable conservation attitude.

Table 7. Level of attitude

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Very Favorable	267	68.11
Favorable	118	30.10
Neutral	7	1.79
TOTAL	392	100.00
Mean = 4.32 (Very Favorable)		

3.4 Relationship between knowledge and conservation attitudes

Analysis of the relationship between knowledge and the attitude of fisherfolk towards coastal conservation showed that there is a significant relationship between the two variables ($r = 0.528$; $p < 0.01$).

Table 8. Relationship between knowledge and attitude

		Knowledge	Attitude
Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	1	.528**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	392	392
Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.528**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	392	392

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

This finding implies that the knowledge and attitude of the fisher folk were related. It further indicates that how well they are informed about the importance of coastal areas influences how they react and behave towards them. The higher level of knowledge they possess, their favorability towards coastal conservation is also higher.

Moreover, a person’s knowledge or point of view may be a technique for predicting his conduct or how he will act. Learning more about the environment has a favorable correlation with a person’s attitude toward protecting it⁽¹⁸⁾.

3.5 Problems and Issues in Coastal areas

The following is the summary of the problems encountered by respondents across the coastal municipalities in Capiz excluding the anthropogenic activities mentioned above. The issues and challenges reported by the respondents were extracted from recorded interviews, which were subsequently transcribed and analyzed.

Table 9. Problems and Issues in Coastal areas

Problems/Issues	Possible Solutions/Interventions
<p>A. Siltation: This issue has been reported in several coastal communities, specifically in Basiao, Agojo, Bantigue, Agtatacay Sur, and Binaobawan. This phenomenon poses significant challenges for the communities, particularly in terms of navigating riverine areas. Furthermore, siltation is impacting the communities’ fishing yields as sediment accumulation leads to the shallowing of water bodies. Siltation affects water distribution; it can create hazards and pose danger to the fisherfolks as well as affect spawning areas⁽¹⁹⁾.</p> <p>From a broader perspective, siltation was also happening in different coastal areas such as in Shandong Peninsula in China where siltation was increasing over the past 15 years⁽²⁰⁾. In India, the use of breakwater system reduced the accumulation of silt in the Fishery Harbour in Konkan Region of Maharashtra, India⁽²¹⁾.</p>	<p>Multiple intervention activities can be conducted to minimize and even stop siltation. Community-based restoration programs such as mangrove planting could help increase buffer zones to prevent rapid sediment flow. On the reactive side, dredging operations can be an instant solution to areas wherein silt has completely blocked waterways.</p>

Continued on next page

Table 9 continued

<p>B. Red Tide: Red tide may not be a consistent problem, but its occurrence and duration are unpredictable. This adversely affects fisherfolks, especially shellfish collectors, leaving them out of work. Red tides can last from anywhere between a few weeks and a few months, so it can potentially cause fishing communities to collapse. The red tide in Costa Rica in 2022 started in early February and didn't really dissipate until late March, so nearly 40% of the five-month high season was affected ⁽²²⁾.</p>	<p>Early warning systems for red tide outbreaks can be highly beneficial for the safety of seafood products and fishers. On the other hand, other preventive programs can be initiated if such a system is non-existent, such as community training on identifying an impending red tide occurrence. Reactive activities could be an enhanced livelihood program for the fisherfolks to alleviate the effects of red tide on them.</p>
<p>C. Shoreline Erosion: Respondents from Binaobawan mentioned shoreline erosion. The shoreline in the area is being eroded by water due to various factors, altering the landscape of the place. In the United States, coastal erosion cause around \$500 million in coastal property loss ⁽²³⁾. Impact of this occurrence in small fisherfolks in coastal areas of Capiz poses huge problems.</p>	<p>Enhanced community-based coastal restoration can help prevent further erosion of the coastal areas. Moreover, physical seawalls and breakwater systems can effectively prevent strong waves from consuming the coastal lands.</p>
<p>D. Freshwater Source: This presents a challenge to the people from Latasan, Jamul-awon, and Gabuc who pointed out this issue specifically. Members of this community depend on collecting rainwater and purchasing freshwater from various locations.</p>	<p>Installation of rainwater harvesting system could solve this problem. Additionally, enhancing the current solution of the residents which is water delivery could also help minimize this problem. Providing the community with storage unit for rainwater can be beneficial.</p>

4 Conclusion

This study provided new insights into the anthropogenic activities of fisherfolks in Capiz uncovering their practices and their impacts on the coastal ecosystems. A potential improvement in the rehabilitation and protection of coastal areas is promising as illustrated by the positive attitude of the fisherfolks towards different conservation activities. It could be a strong foundation for developing coastal management activities and strategies in various coastal municipalities of Capiz. Strong knowledge of coastal resources underscores the potential efforts that the fisherfolks themselves can contribute to the management activities. The community may just need an enforced policy for more effective and efficient conservation efforts.

However, harmful activities still threaten the conservation efforts being undertaken. Six (6) harmful and seven (7) beneficial activities have been observed. This destructive activity requires stricter regulations with more interventions and further community education. The positive correlation between the knowledge and attitude of the respondents implies that enhancing the awareness of the community of environmental impacts could lead to more conservation behaviors.

To further the conservation efforts in coastal areas, enhanced compliance checks on unhealthy environmental activities based on the findings of this study and encouraging efforts to preserve the environment are crucial. Moreover, take advantage of the highly informed and largely positive attitude towards conservation in the community through engagement of the people in projects to do with conservation through motivation. Also, establish detailed strategies of how to handle other major environmental challenges that face the world including siltation, red tide, shoreline erosion and water shortage. Through these areas of focus, Capiz can bring about sustainable positive change in the region together with the proper management of the coastal region resources.

Acknowledgements

The research was under the Fisheries and Food Research Development Center and funded by Research Development and Extension (RDE) of Capiz State University.

References

- 1) Häder D, Banaszak A, Villafaña V, Villafaña V, Narvarte M, González R, et al. Anthropogenic pollution of aquatic ecosystems: Emerging problems with global implications. *Science of the total environment*. 2020;713. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.136586>.
- 2) Hammond T, Ortiz-Jimenez C, Smith J. Anthropogenic change alters ecological relationships via interactive changes in stress physiology and behavior within and among organisms. *Integrative and comparative biology*. 2020;60(1):57–69. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1093/icb/icaa001>.
- 3) Jurelevicius D, Cotta S, Montezzi L, Dias A, Mason O, Picão R, et al. Enrichment of potential pathogens in marine microbiomes with different degrees of anthropogenic activity. *Environmental Pollution*. 2021;268. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.115757>.
- 4) Malone T, Newton A. The Globalization of Cultural Eutrophication in the Coastal Ocean: Causes and Consequences. *Frontiers in Marine Science*. 2020;7. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2020.00670>.
- 5) Hauser-Davis R, Wosnick N. Climate Change Implications for Metal and Metalloid Dynamics in Aquatic Ecosystems and its Context within the Decade of Ocean Sciences. *Water*. 2022;14(15). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/w14152415>.

- 6) Digest E. What are anthropogenic activities?. 2023. Available from: <https://energydigest.co.uk/blog/what-are-anthropogenic-activities>.
- 7) Kennish M. Drivers of Change in Estuarine and Coastal Marine Environments: An Overview. *Open Journal of Ecology*. 2021;11:224–239. Available from: <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation?paperid=107450#:~:text=The%20list%20of%20anthropogenic%20drivers,%2C%20nutrients%2C%20organic%20carbon%2C%20and>.
- 8) Arcega I, Malayang S, Mirasol P, Casios A. Roxas City, the Seafood Capital of the Philippines: Myth or Fact? *Asian Journal of Applied Science and Technology*. 2021;5(3):213–222. Available from: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3942831.
- 9) Prodanova N, Naslednikova M, Tarasova O. Study of the impact of anthropogenic activities on the environment: Problems and prospects of sustainable nature management. *E3S Web of Conferences*. 2023;420:1–10. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202342004001>.
- 10) Philippine fisheries profile. 2021. Available from: <https://www.bfar.da.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/2022-Philippine-Fisheries-Profile.pdf>.
- 11) Rao GP, Vardhan HMN, Shastry MPM. Waste management using reward system. *Journal of Critical Reviews*. 2020;83:4935–4938. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348390926_Waste_Management_Using_Reward_System.
- 12) Napata RP, Espectato LN, Serofia GD. Closed season policy in Visayan Sea, Philippines: A second look. 2020;187. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2020.105115>.
- 13) Abakah S, Owusu V. Impacts of illegal fishing and ocean dependence on the livelihoods of coastal fisherfolk in Ghana. *Ghana Journal of Geography*. 2023;15. Available from: <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/gjg/article/view/244926>.
- 14) Mance D, Vilke S, Debelić B. Sustainable Governance of Coastal Areas and Tourism Impact on Waste Production: Panel Analysis of Croatian Municipalities. *Sustainability*. 2020;12(18). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12187243>.
- 15) Loch T, Riechers M. Integrating indigenous and local knowledge in management and research on coastal ecosystems in the Global South: A literature review. *Ocean & Coastal Management*. 2021;212. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2021.105821>.
- 16) Ali M, Malik A, Rahim A. Environmental knowledge and attitude of coastal community in decision making to participate in mangrove rehabilitation in Sinjai District South Sulawesi Indonesia. *International Journal of Sustainable Development*. 2022;17:2579–2584. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/366977652_Environmental_Knowledge_and_Attitude_of_Coastal_Community_in_Decision_Making_to_Participate_in_Mangrove_Rehabilitation_in_Sinjai_District_South_Sulawesi_Indonesia.
- 17) Dealy HR, Jarvis RM, Young T, Maharaj K, Petterson M. The role of hope and conservation attitudes in current conservation actions and future conservation intentions. *Discover Sustainability*. 2024;5. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s43621-024-00186-6#:~:text=Conservation%20attitudes%20to%20be,get%20involved%20in%20conservation%20volunteering>.
- 18) Hernanda T, Absori A, Azhari AF, Wardiono K, Arlinwibowo J. Relationship between knowledge and affection for the environment: A meta-analysis. *European Journal of Educational Research*. 2023;12(2):1071–1084. Available from: https://pdf.eu-jer.com/EU-JER_12_2_1071.pdf.
- 19) Demystified: Siltation in irrigation infrastructure. 2022. Available from: <https://www.irrigationauthority.go.ke/2022/02/25/demystified-siltation-in-irrigation-infrastructure/>.
- 20) Zhang Z, Gao W, Li P, Liu J, Xu Y, Wei X, et al. Influencing Factors of Submarine Scouring and Siltation Changes in Offshore Area of Shandong Peninsula. *Water*. 2023;15(3). Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3390/w15030435>.
- 21) Sinha S, Shukla V, Singh A. Hydrodynamics and Sediment Modelling for a Fishery Harbour in Konkan Region of Maharashtra, India. *Journal of Water Engineering and Management*. 2022;3(1). Available from: <https://jweam.in/volume-3-issue-1/hydrodynamics-and-sediment-modelling-for-a-fishery-harbour-in-konkan-region-of-maharashtra-india/>.
- 22) How does red tide affect fishing?. 2022. Available from: <https://www.centralamericafishing.com/what-is-red-tide/>.
- 23) Toolkit UCR. Coastal erosion. 2021. Available from: <https://toolkit.climate.gov/topics/coastal-flood-risk/coastal-erosion>.